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The Role of Parents in Modular Learning Modality: A Narrative Inquiry
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Abstract

This qualitative study delves into the experiences of four mothers navigating their children's education during the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on modular learning modalities. Through in-depth interviews, four main themes emerged: Uncertainties of Mother-Mentors, Preparation of Activities, Actual Mentoring, and Accepting the Challenge. The findings highlight the initial apprehension and challenges faced by mothers when transitioning to modular learning, including concerns about balancing work and assisting multiple children with their studies. Despite these uncertainties, the mothers exhibited resilience and dedication, proactively preparing conducive learning environments and adapting their routines to facilitate their children's education at home. The study underscores the pivotal role of parental involvement in supporting children's education during crisis situations, emphasizing the unwavering commitment of caregivers to prioritize their children's academic success. Despite the psychological impact of the pandemic, the mothers remained steadfast in their determination to uphold learning continuity and ensure their children's future prospects. This study provides valuable insights into the experiences of mothers navigating modular learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the need for innovative strategies to support families and ensure equitable access to quality education in times of uncertainty and disruption.

Keywords: COVID 19, Modular Learning, Parents, Modality Narrative Inquiry

Introduction:

The society we live in today might be frightening for a child to confront on their own. Parents are the most influential and powerful role models. Mothers play the most fundamental role of an educator in a child's early life. They continue to be the heart of the child's education right from their childhood to their growing up years.

Parental involvement is an important factor for student achievement in traditional school settings. Parental support has been shown to have a substantial impact on the learners' success in their online learning environment (Mavri, et al., 2023). Many teachers, families, and students were caught off guard by this abrupt shift, which exposed some of the difficulties and concerns associated with increased parental participation while engaging and assisting their children in various levels and forms of distance learning (Garbe, et al., 2020). Despite the fact that several terminologies have been used in the field, for the purposes of this study, the terms modular distance learning and online, virtual and e- learning are interchangeable (Moore, et al., 2011).

Based on Department of Education No. 12, s. 2020 the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the light of COVID 19 Pandemic emphasizes the interventions that will respond on basic education challenges. It ensures the personnel's health, safety, and well-being of teachers as well as adjustments on K-12 Curriculum using the MELCS (Most Essential Learning Competencies). In this COVID-19 outbreak, to meet the needs and adapt to the new system of education as a fortress of learning continuity plan the Modular Distance Learning is being implemented across the country. Modular distance learning features individualized instruction that allows learners to use self-learning modules (SLMS) in print or digital format/ electronic copy, whichever is applicable to the learner.

Based on the study conducted by Ambayon & Millenes (2020), modular instruction is more operative in the teaching- learning method as equated to usual teaching approaches because in this modular approach the students learn in their own stride. It was unrestricted self-learning style in which reinforcement was measured at a particular instant, a comment was provided to practice exercise, which stimulates the students and builds curiosity in them. Hence, this kind of learning modality increases the student-centered approach in learning and accepts greater responsibility for learning.

During this pandemic, parents' initiatives and creativity helps our learners learn even during war. Since education is about learning skills and knowledge. It also means helping people to learn how to do things and support them to think about what they learn. Through education, the knowledge of society, country, and of the world is passed on from generation to generation. In recent years, there has been a transition from teacher-led to student-centered curriculum, with an emphasis on the knowledge, skills, and competencies that students possess upon completion of a course or program, as well as a change in the course design process (Scheurs & Dumbraveanu, 2014).

The strategy of modular learning focuses on learning outcomes, and its effectiveness is dependent on connecting objectives to student learning and course design. Section 1 Article XIV of 1987 Philippine Constitution, it states that "the States shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all" However, the implementation of modular instruction fostered various challenges to teachers, students, and parents. Economic resources are a potential barrier to parental involvement in remote learning settings (Cabardo, et al., 2022). The study of Dangle and Somauang (2020) showed that the main challenges that emerged were lack of school funding in the production and delivery of modules, students struggle with self-studying, and parents lack of knowledge to academically guide their children.

Parents have conflicting feelings about remote learning. Some parents are more involved with their children's academics than others, and some perceive this as a burden, as one of the parents remarked: Classes are held at set times, and since I also need to worry about things like making a living, I can't devote all my time to helping my children with their homework. Hence, it is evident that there were struggles associated with the use of modular distance learning. This only means that despite the crisis that we were facing, education must continue. The goal of this study is to explore and inquire narrative experiences of parents with children having Modular Learning Modality during the COVID 19 outbreak.

Literature Review:

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented unprecedented challenges to education systems worldwide, affecting millions of students across various countries. In response to lockdowns and restrictions, governments have implemented diverse strategies to ensure continuity in education, including distance learning modalities and tele-education programs (Dayagbil, et al., 2021). Amid these changes, parental involvement has emerged as a crucial factor in supporting children's education during these challenging times.

Lockdown measures have disrupted traditional modes of education, compelling governments to explore alternative methods to facilitate learning (Oda Abunamous, et al., 2022). Various countries have adopted distance education modalities, including online platforms, televised lessons, and printed assignments, to ensure continued learning for students. Additionally, awareness campaigns and initiatives have been launched to educate parents, teachers, and students about the transition to remote learning and provide support to those lacking access to technology.

Parental Involvement and Student Achievement:

Research indicates a strong correlation between parental involvement and student achievement. Studies have shown that parental participation positively influences academic outcomes, with parental expectations playing a significant role in shaping children's educational success. Factors such as parental self-efficacy and perceptions of school invitations influence the extent of parental involvement in children's education.

Despite the importance of parental involvement, various challenges exist, particularly in low-income countries like Pakistan and the Philippines. Economic constraints, limited access to technology, and historical factors contribute to barriers in parental engagement (Baker, et al., 2016). However, initiatives such as Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) and home-school collaboration programs aim to bridge the gap between parents and schools, fostering a supportive environment for children's learning.

The COVID-19 pandemic has underscored the significance of parental involvement in supporting children's education during times of crisis. While challenges persist, initiatives aimed at enhancing parental engagement offer opportunities to strengthen the partnership between parents and schools. By addressing barriers and promoting collaborative efforts, policymakers and educators can ensure that every child receives the support needed to thrive academically, even amidst challenging circumstances.

Methodology:

Design

This study utilized the narrative inquiry. It was a term that subsumes a group of approaches that in turn rely on the written or spoken words or visual representation of individuals. These approaches typically focused on the lives of individuals as told through their own stories. Clandinin and Connelly (2000) define it as a way of understanding and inquiring into experience through collaboration between researcher and participants, over time, in a place or series of places, and in social interaction with millieus (Clandinin & Connelly 2000).

A narrative study examines "the ways humans see the world" Clandinin & Connelly (2000) provides researchers with new information about the phenomenon (Creswell, 2012). "For educators looking for personal experiences in actual school settings, narrative research offers practical, specific insights," according to (Creswell 2012). Narrative

research can focus on one or more individuals' experiences. This study seeks to explain the experiences and role of parents in the conduct of Modular Learning Modality.

This method attempts to set aside biases and preconceived assumptions about human experiences, feelings, and responses to a particular situation. These include interviews, visiting places, and observation. The main tools in data gathering were interview/unstructured questionnaires. Constructed response questionnaire with open-ended questions used to probe the respondents' experience in the modular learning modality.

Environment

The study was conducted in Basak Elementary School. Parents were the external stakeholders of the school. Considering the personal connection with the people in this place, the researcher chooses this research site. It has a population of 320 learners, around 11 teachers including the researcher, One guidance counsellor, One non-teaching personnel and One school head. The place was located at the northern part of Cebu. Considering the comfort of the researcher. The researcher chooses this school for ease and comfort.

Participants

The respondents of the study were four mothers only from Basak Elementary School. The mothers will be selected using the purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling, because the researcher relied on her own judgement when choosing members of the population participated in the surveys. The number of participants for qualitative studies was generally much smaller than that of quantitative studies because the purpose of qualitative research was not to generalize the results. This section provides the profile of the identified parents of Basak Elementary School, Basak, Catmon, Cebu as to age and gender, grade level of children, educational status, and employment status.

Table 1

Profile of Participants

Code Names	Age	Grade Level of child/children	Educational Status	Employment Status
Jovelyn	40	Grade 2 ,3, 7,10	High school Graduate	housewife
Colleen	29	Grade 2 & Kinder	College level	housewife
Nimfa	37	Grade 5 & 6	College graduate	Regular employee
Gemma	41	Grade 6 & 12	High school graduate	Regular employee

The parents were selected according to their educational status and employment to find how these factors affect their bearing on the role.

Table 2

Inclusion- Exclusion Criteria of Participants

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
1. A mother who graduated college and working.	1. Mothers who are not willing or too shy to share their stories
2. A mother who graduated basic education and working.	2. Mothers who have comorbidities that could bias the results of the study.
3. A college level mother but not working.	
4. A mother who graduated basic education and working.	

Accordingly, purposeful sampling was used and the number of participants was small to gain insights into the phenomena under investigation. It requires the creation of a researcher made criteria that was best suitable to target the informants who have firsthand experiences.

Instrument

To carry out this study, the researcher considered herself as the primary instrument for the success of this endeavor. The instrument used a semi structured interview guide. The researcher used a semi detailed interview guide as its secondary instrument that contains the following questions composed of preliminary, developmental and wrap-up. There were two prepared questions for preliminary, five for developmental as it contains the main intention of the study and another one question for wrap-up. The researchers prepared open-ended questions as the basic tool in collecting the data during face to face interview. The researcher simply uses recorder (cell phone) for recording of what she heard during the interview, the researcher used reflexive journal for keeping a personal record of the process and transcriptions.

Data Gathering Procedures

There were three phases of the data gathering procedures. The preliminary, actual data collection and data management. The implementation of these three phases serves the researcher as guide on accomplishing this research task.

Preliminary Data Gathering

First, the researcher presented to the Dean the three titles. Then the approved title was given to me and advised to proceed in making research study for chapters I-III. Afterwards, the researcher sent papers to the adviser for corrections and underwent research consultation with the Dean before the design hearing. The researcher also made a letter addressed to the Dean and to the District Supervisor and to School Principal for approval of the study. Then, made a letter for each respondent for them to be prepared and aware of. The purpose of the study was explained. This enhanced smooth and easy contact to all the respondents.

Actual Data Gathering

Then the second phase of data gathering was the implementation phase in which the researcher explained the purpose of the study to enhance smooth and easy contact to all the respondents. Since the researcher was using face to face platform in the data collection, the researcher made sure that the guidelines set forth by the Inter Agency Task Force (IATF) such as social distancing and the necessary health protocols must be observed. The researcher set the scheduled for an interview of the participants depending on their available time. The duration of the interview was ten minutes for each mother.

The researcher administered the open-ended interview. The same open-ended questions were asked to all interviewees. This approach facilitates faster interviews that can be more easily analyzed and compared. The responses were recorded, can be compared, and analyzed easily because of the uniformity of the questions asked and will be reviewed for consolidation, analysis, and interpretation.

Post Data Gathering

After the collection of data, the researcher played the recorded responses as her guide on making a stories of participants. The researcher remains focused on each participant's story. The respondents' responses were organized and analyzed by the researcher. The researcher reports on participants' life experiences as told through their stories. Then reconstructs the individuals' stories and tells them in a chronological order with a beginning, middle, and end. The results would be hopefully be the basis for the enhancement of learning outcomes. All of the information was stored in a digital format. The researcher's cell phone was used to record the interview, which was then uploaded to a laptop computer. The study's data was kept and will not be destroyed until the thesis is approved in its entirety.

Data Analysis

Qualitative procedures were employed in this narrative inquiry. To determine the experience and role of mother-mentors using modular learning modality in teaching, responses will be consolidated based on the similarity of their thoughts and was merged descriptions and statements synthesizing their ideas. The researcher did the theming, and data synthesizing. Then, those were collated, tabulated, and analyzed based on the statement of the problem. Considering the three dimensions of narrative inquiry: temporality, the personal and social, and the location where the researcher mediates stories while maintaining the spirit of flirtation. The analysis of empirical materials was often conducted using a four-step process. First, an early explanation of the temporal and geographical boundaries. Second, a description of the participants. Third, interpreting remarks and using the participant's verbatim language-gathered. Lastly, to tell the story regarding what this researcher think was happening and why. Thinking narratively during analysis involves negotiating relationships, negotiating purposes, negotiating ways to be useful, and negotiating transitions while keeping in mind theoretical, methodological, and interpretive considerations (Connelly & Clandinin, 2020). Connelly and Clandinin (2000) recommended three analytical tools for narrative inquiry: broadening, burrowing, and storying and restorying. They used these analytical tools to analyze and piece together the narrative material they gathered. They transitioned from interim field texts to research text with the help of these interpretive devices. Individual interviews were the most commonly used data collection method in this research and the foremost method in narrative inquiry in particular, as the researcher understands that the interviewees told stories based on their narrative schema that reflects personal knowledge and experiences. An inductive approach was used to analyze the qualitative data collected from the in-depth interviews. Therefore, broader themes framing each research question along with coinciding conclusions emerged from chunking pieces of related interview data using thematic analysis procedure.

Findings:

The main method chosen to investigate the problem was through interviewing parents who assessed their children's education in modular learning modality. Before making a careful and detailed search for information into this study, qualitative discussions on related studies were used as foundations for the development of research questions and interview topics. The study was qualitative by nature of the research question. A narrative research study was used. The sampling method was a purposeful sample of four parents who have been in their role in

giving assistance to their children's schoolwork. The researcher conducted an initial ten minute talk to schedule the one on one interview and go over the interview questions followed by an in depth interviews with in two weeks after the initial interview. This study had limitations because of its constructivist view, research site, and small number of participants.

On the basis of the results and analysis, four distinctive features were developed: Uncertainty of Events, Preparation of Activities, Mentoring and Accepting the Challenge

Theme 1: Uncertainties of Mother- Mentors

Findings provided evidence that these four mothers encountered challenges on the bearing of their role in assisting their children during modular learning. When the pandemic strikes and when they knew that the mode of learning was through modules, all mothers were worried.

"There's a lot of questions that lingers on my mind like should I enrol my kids or do I have to wait for the face to face classes. Do kids learned something on this modular approach that there is really a difference when the teacher will guide/teach. I'm really worried that I might not be able to perform multi-task." (Colleen line 11-27).

"I work 8 hours, instead of resting when I get home I have something else to do. Good if I only have one kid, but they are 4, 2 are studying and 2 are still young." (Nimfa, line statement 163-176).

"I am worried and sad that my child might not be able to learn on this modular approach." (Gemma, line statement 288-292).

"I was worried because I still had no idea how I would teach my child." (Jovelyn, line statement 414-417).

According to Hoover-Dempsey et al., (2017) parents' beliefs of their time, energy, abilities, and knowledge have an impact on their engagement behaviors, such as the activities and choices they make in connection to their children's education. Finally, (Green et al., 2019) investigated the ability of the Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler's revised theoretical model of the parental involvement process (Walker et al., 2018) to predict the types and levels of parental involvement during the elementary and middle school years in a recent article on the topic of parents' motivations for involvement in their children's education.

Theme 2: Preparation of Activities

Findings revealed that despite the struggles they have encountered all of them supported their children's journey in the modular learning modality. Parents act as the scaffolding of learning at home. To make sure that there is a smooth flow of the learning process at home, these four mothers have one thing in common in terms of preparation on this mode of learning as they said

"I prepared School supplies, study area, table and schedule of activities so that they will be guided on the things to do every day." (Collen, line statement 32-40).

"I prepared a study area or a class home for them and provide their needed/ class materials." (Nimfa, line statement 184-220).

"I prepared the things that was suggested by the teacher like place where in they will answer their lessons and the schedule of activities on what they will do each day & etc." (Gemma, line statement 306-315).

"I prepared a place in our house which is away from disturbance, school supplies and the time to start in, answering the module." (Jovelyn, line statement 429-437).

Mothers were responsible for monitoring the different learning activities and to provide what their children's need. Due to the crisis, schools and colleges (Saeed, 2020), and low-cost schools are on the verge of closing (Yousafzai, 2020). A curriculum that includes parental advice and COVID-19 related knowledge can be augmented with the creation of a national education system in response to coronavirus outbreaks and school closures. This would aid in the improvement of school systems as a whole, as well as ensuring learning achievement at home. Based on the results, they never give up in supporting their kids and this is a great stories of struggles for a great mother. They can have scars, they can go through turbulent times and have courage to win the battles of everyday lives.

Theme 3: Actual Mentoring

Findings presented that the bearings of four mothers in assisting their children on the modular learning affects their daily lives and find remedies to everything as these four mothers uttered that

"On the first day of modular learning, I have adjusted my usual waking up mood." (Collen, line statement 40-70)

"Similarly, On the first day of modular learning I woke up 4:30 in the morning to have an ample time in fixing the things that needs to be done." (Nimfa, line statement 190-220)

"On the first day of modular learning, I woke up early because I have to go to work afterwards. Before I left them for work I gave them a piece of advice." (Gemma, line statement 315-344).

"On the first day of modular learning, I awoke early in the morning and prepared meals for breakfast." (Jovelyn, line statement 437-491).

They further shared that amid anticipated interruptions they ensure that the learning of their kids will continue using this set-up. Colleen give her kids emotional support. Then she tried to balance her time. She tried her very best that despite the different household chores, she spared time for her kids in their modular lessons and if there were some topic which was unfamiliar to her she search it on the google. This study supports the mother-teacher concept proposed by DPS Kolar and Road Bhopa, which states that mothers understand and adjust for their children. They were always concerned for their children's well-being and were willing to make sacrifices to ensure their success. This finding also indicated that COVID 19 had a significant impact on the psychological well-being, emotions, and family relationships of mothers (Clark et al., 2021). Similarly, Kalsoom, (2021) stated that, as a result of the epidemic, mothers face difficulties such as balancing work and family life, finding space and resources to teach their children, and learning new skills to teach their children.

Findings indicated that despite the struggles they have encountered, all mothers supported their children's journey in the modular learning modality. Three out of four mothers do not have background in teaching. So they tried their best to teach their child to learn. Mothers are well positioned to provide children with an interesting learning environment and to assist them with their educational problems and needs. Despite their hectic schedules, all four mothers stated that they monitored and follow up on the different module activities that their children needed to complete. Gonzales, (2020) stated that the Department of Education recommended that parents served as motivators and checkers to see if their children had completed their modules. Two out of four respondents stated that work-life balance and time management are crucial tools for ensuring the smooth flow of mentoring.

Mothers provide appropriate solutions to any problems that may arise. According to (Flack et al., 2020), teachers should be concerned about their pupils' emotional well-being during the pandemic, which means teachers should focus more on Maslow's hierarchy rather than Bloom's taxonomy. Mothers generally recognized the benefits of teaching their children. They were able to spend more time on their children's education and bonding. Mothers and their children were found to spend more time at home with each other. This situation suggests that, despite the increased strain, mothers were able to find the silver lining. In spite of the advantages of this situation, Kokhanova et al., (2021) discovered that many parents were dissatisfied with distance learning because of the lack of complete contact and engagement with students and teachers. Furthermore, according to Abuhammad (2020), most parents were opposed to remote learning due to personal, technical, logistical, and financial barriers.

Theme 4: Accepting the Challenge

These four mothers explore a new world of becoming a mentor and they had left no choice except to embrace the new roles. Though there were struggles meet as stated by each participants but it has positively impact in the continuity for kids learning during this period of unusual time. Findings provided evidence to support the idea in the literature, introduce in Chapter 2 that people have been affected in one way or another since the emergence of the coronavirus illness 2019 (COVID 19). Lockdowns have had a significant impact on the lives of people of all ages and occupations. The flare-up has also impacted the educational system around the world, affecting 1, 576, 021, 818 students in 188 countries (UNESCO, 2020). The lockdowns have presented governments with an unprecedented difficulty in ensuring that learning continues (Chang &Yano, 2020). Several countries have used a variety of strategies to address educational issues.

In a similar manner these four mothers stated that

"In spite of the challenges that we are facing I decided to let my kids pursue their studies because I dont want that their learning will be stopped for I know the importance of education in my children's life." (Collen, line 139-152)

"Whereas, education plays an important role of my children's life so despite the pandemic I decided to enrol my kids for them to continue learning." (Nimfa, line statement 273-281)

"In spite of the challenges that we are facing I decided to let my kids pursue their studies because I dont want that their learning will be stopped for I know the importance of education in my children's life." (Gemma, line statement 395-402)

"I believe that the child with wisdom will go far and because of that even with a pandemic I decided educating my kids to learn." (Jovelyn, line statement 548-557).

Finding shows that at the height of the pandemic, these four mother's passion and purpose in educating their children was unstoppable. The magnitude of effort and persistence parallels the magnitude of accomplishments that parents have executed and gained while battling two critical elements in our community development, the health and education.

The findings of the study also supported the idea that school characteristics, as well as the nature of the general school invitations, influence the formation of parental roles. Invitations from the school, teacher, and/or child were also found to be effective contextual motivators for parental involvement by Hoover-Dempsey et al. Finally, according to Hoover-Dempsey et al., parents' beliefs of their time, energy, abilities, and knowledge have an impact on their engagement behaviors, such as the activities and choices they make in connection to their children's education. Finally, Green et al., (2019) investigated the ability of the Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler's revised theoretical model of the parental involvement process (Walker et al., 2018) to predict the types and levels of parental involvement during the elementary and middle school years in a recent article on the topic of parents' motivations for involvement in their children's education.

Based on the parenting stress models by Abidin, (2010), the stress perceived by parents due to distance learning was likely to affect students' perception of distance learning and the perceived threat of COVID-19 was a stressor for parents which affected their stress due to distance learning. It is understandable that the wave of innovations in learning is not always convenient most especially to a working mom since they cannot facilitate learning the way some mothers do and therefore it is necessary for them to identify what were the things that needs to be done first. When it came to their children's education, most mothers agreed that they needed to manage their time because kids learning is one of their priorities.

Discussion:

The qualitative study conducted sheds light on the experiences of four mothers as they navigate their children's education during the unprecedented challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic, with a specific focus on modular learning approaches. By conducting in-depth interviews, the study identified and explored four key themes: Uncertainties of Mother-Mentors, Preparation of Activities, Actual Mentoring, and Accepting the Challenge.

The theme of Uncertainties of Mother-Mentors reveals the initial apprehensions and anxieties faced by mothers when confronted with the transition to modular learning. This theme underscores the multifaceted challenges these mothers encountered, including the juggling act of balancing work responsibilities while providing educational support to multiple children. It also underscores the significant impact of parental beliefs on their engagement behaviors, aligning with existing research on the crucial role of parental involvement in education.

Preparation of Activities underscores the proactive measures taken by mothers to create conducive learning environments for their children at home. Despite the inherent difficulties, these mothers ensured that their children had access to essential resources and dedicated spaces for studying. This theme highlights the pivotal role of parents as facilitators of their children's educational journey, echoing recommendations for heightened parental involvement, especially during times of crisis like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Actual Mentoring delves into the daily adjustments and sacrifices made by mothers to effectively support their children's education in the modular learning setting. It showcases the unwavering dedication and resilience of these mothers as they navigated unfamiliar territory, often without prior teaching experience. This theme sheds light on the profound psychological impact of the pandemic on mothers and their families, while also underscoring their steadfast commitment to ensuring their children's academic success.

Accepting the Challenge encapsulates the overarching resilience and determination exhibited by these mothers as they embraced their new roles as mentors amidst unprecedented challenges. Despite facing numerous uncertainties and obstacles, these mothers remained steadfast in prioritizing their children's education, recognizing its enduring significance. This theme resonates with broader discussions surrounding the global ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic on educational systems, emphasizing the urgent need for innovative strategies to uphold learning continuity.

This study offers valuable insights into the experiences of mothers navigating modular learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. It illuminates the indispensable role of parental involvement in supporting children's education during times of crisis, highlighting the resilience and dedication of caregivers in surmounting challenges. Furthermore, the study underscores the imperative of incorporating parental perspectives and experiences into the development of effective education policies and interventions, particularly in the face of uncertainty and disruption.

Conclusion:

This qualitative study provides a comprehensive exploration of the experiences of four mothers grappling with the complexities of their children's education amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, specifically within the context of modular learning modalities. Through in-depth interviews, four distinct themes emerged: Uncertainties of Mother-Mentors, Preparation of Activities, Actual Mentoring, and Accepting the Challenge.

The findings of this study shed light on the initial apprehensions faced by mothers when transitioning to modular learning, highlighting the myriad challenges they encountered while striving to balance work commitments and provide educational support to their children. Despite these uncertainties, the mothers exhibited remarkable resilience and determination, proactively preparing conducive learning environments and adapting their routines to facilitate their children's education at home.

Furthermore, the study underscores the crucial role of parental involvement in supporting children's learning during times of crisis, emphasizing the unwavering dedication and sacrifices made by caregivers to ensure their children's academic success. Despite the psychological impact of the pandemic, the mothers remained steadfast in their commitment to prioritizing education, recognizing its long-term importance for their children's future.

This study offers valuable insights into the experiences of mothers navigating modular learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the need for innovative strategies to uphold learning continuity in the face of unprecedented challenges. By incorporating parental perspectives and experiences into education policies and interventions, policymakers and educators can better address the needs of families and ensure equitable access to quality education, even during times of uncertainty and disruption.

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